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Report on Exploration Workshops

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Executive summary

As part of WP4 of the HOLiFOOD project, three Living Labs (LL) have been established, linked to WP1, WP3 and WP6, respectively. Each LL goes through the three different phases of Exploration, Experimentation and Evaluation during the four years of the project. This Deliverable report presents the set up and results of the first phase of the Living Labs, i.e., the Exploration phase.

The LL development and composition mostly followed the Guidelines which had been set up in Task 4.1, and were described in Deliverable 4.1. For the Exploration phase, LL1 and LL3 organized a workshop, and LL2 has set up a Delphi Survey, each aimed to retrieve the needs and experiences from stakeholders, and to co-create a tailor-made action plan, that addresses the identified needs.

The workshop of LL1 was based on the identification of needs of stakeholders as related to emerging risk identification (ERI) models and tools (to be developed in WP1). The workshop not only aimed to list stakeholder needs, but also to find ways to best address them, and to recognize possible problems that could be encountered. The Delphi survey of LL2 focused on the identification of stakeholder's expectations in term of holistic risk assessment dimensions, preferential methods of risk aggregation, and formats of holistic assessment outputs.

The workshop of LL3 was focused on the identification of technical requirements of stakeholders related to the ERI infrastructures, in terms of data, models and computation.

This Deliverable report shows how Co-Creation acts as a “key-component” when including the analysis of the common problems and needs, involving key players in the ideation and co-design through brainstorming sessions and focus groups; while the quantitative data collection (interviews and questionnaires) is also crucial for the baseline developed of the research processes.

1 Introduction

1.1 HOLiFOOD WP4

The overall objective of WP4 entitled “Stakeholder engagement and codesign in living labs” is to establish three Living Labs (LLs) following the innovation development phase approach which consists of three phases: exploration, experimentation and evaluation. This co-creation activity is particularly necessary for a wide variety of food system actors to work together to facilitate the early identification, assessment and mitigation of risks related to existing and emerging food safety hazards.

The three LLs are planned to be conducted in both virtual and face-to-face modes and are aimed at addressing three different priorities: 1) Identification and monitoring of emerging food safety risks (LL1), 2) Holistic risk assessment and acceptance (LL2), 3) Co-design of the platform for emerging risk identification (LL3).

The respective contents of each specific LL are addressed to the following HOLiFOOD WPs:

LL1: WP1 “Big Data technologies and Artificial Intelligence (AI) for food safety detection and prevention”,

LL2: WP2 “Holistic risk assessment for regulation”,

LL3: WP6 “Integrated Decision Making & Mitigation”.

The overall objective the HOLiFOOD project can be achieved through these three LLs by bridging the gap between research and practice by facilitating discussions between stakeholders, hereby systematically integrating the multi-actor approach (MAA).

1.2 Living Labs Introduction

In the course of HOLiFOOD project, the use of Living Labs (LL) as co-creation approach is implemented throughout the entire project. HOLiFOOD uses the following definition of LL - based on the European Network of Living labs (<https://enoll.org/>):

“User-centered, open innovation ecosystems based on systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in arenas where both open innovation and user innovation processes can be studied”.

LLs operate as intermediaries among the so called quadruple Helix (Civil society, Public Administration, Business and Research & Education) for joint value co-creation or validation to scale up innovation and businesses. They act as ‘brokers’ between citizens and organizations (academia, local government, private companies etc.), ensuring that each participant is able to contribute with its knowledge and experience.

HOLiFOOD implements a multi-actor codesign approach, using the LL methodology, to ensure stakeholders needs and requirements are considered throughout the project: stakeholders are indeed involved in setting the research objectives, research activities, innovation roll-out and translational activities.

Co-creation in LLs is a method of tackling real-life problems, as this methodology allows complex issues to be unbundled by submitting them to multi-actor groups that can grasp all the nuances. A structured co-design process is followed throughout the project, defined as a "transparent process of value creation in ongoing, productive collaboration with, and supported by all relevant parties, with end-users playing a central role and covering all stages of a development process".

Especially if we talk about food, new methods are needed that take into account the increasingly connected and convergent arena of the food system for adequately addressing new challenges, and to develop new solutions with a holistic and trans-sectoral approach. Resorting to collaboration thus allows the views of experts from different ecosystems to be interwoven, finding common ground in the HOLiFOOD project goal.

Another interesting issue is that co-creation activities highlight that actors do not have all the answers, so it is beneficial for all to listen to different points of view and work together to find solutions.

In this context, the use of co-creation tools in the Living Labs is crucial to foster creativity, especially in the exploration phase, to find innovative solutions and to improve the engagement of actors.

1.3 What Exploration Living Lab means in HOLiFOOD

The exploratory approach of the LLs was translated within the project activity into an inductive content analysis which implied the collection and analysis of data without specific categories of experts or preconceived theories on the topic. This flexibility went very well with the co-creation approach and created a well-identified space within the specific research activities.

Co-creation therefore made it possible to guide the researcher's analysis to identify emerging patterns, themes and concepts that can be experimented in the next phase. Moreover, this approach helped identify patterns, categories, or themes that may not have been considered at the early stage of the WP's activities and ensured that researchers explored multiple perspectives and viewpoints.

On the other side of the coin, the inductive approach declined as co-creation activity can be time-consuming compared with a traditional analysis. Another disadvantage, of course, can be represented by the influence of researcher's personal biases and preconceptions, but these are constantly overcome by the analysis and wrap-up sessions done after the labs.

In contrast to a deductive, top-down approach, which starts with a theoretical framework and tests hypotheses, this bottom-up approach is more exploratory and open-ended and leaves space to the real contributions gathered from the MAA.

1.4 Criteria for co-creation modalities selection

For each of the three LL, the most suitable co-creation methodology was selected based on several criteria/aspects, being:

- The mode of participation (in-person, virtual or hybrid labs)
To ensure everyone's participation, it is critical to identify the right tools. Especially in virtual LLs, it is more complex to achieve sufficient levels of engagement for the exploration activities. Several tools are available.
- The thematic priorities of each workshop (depending on the relevant WP)
Each LL must explore the specific priorities set by the relevant WP, so co-creation tools and methods need to be appropriate for the intended purpose.

Conducting exploratory activities on highly technical and/or scientific topics should be made as accessible as possible to all participants through tailor made methodologies.

- The number of participants for each Living Lab
Participant management is a crucial aspect to consider when setting up a workshop or other way of stakeholder interaction. To give voice to all participants and not make them feel excluded, the methodologies and tools must be appropriate to their numbers. The number of participants particularly impacts whether they are divided into break out groups and how many of them are needed to facilitate the activities.
- The background/entities of the participants
The participants in the LLs and their affiliated realities affect the methodologies used. Specifically, the level of expertise that must have been commensurate among the various participants must be considered when choosing co-creation methodologies. In addition, different participants can influence each other and learn from each other, and in this sense the methodologies must be an appropriate support.

2 Methodology

2.1 Set up Living Labs

2.1.1 Living Lab topics

As part of WP4 (task 4.1), three Living Labs – each with a LL manager and LL facilitator - have been set up in the first year of the project.

Table 1 presents the LL topics, linked WP, LL manager and LL facilitator.

Table 1: Topics and responsibilities of the 3 LLs

LL	WP	Topic	Organization LL manager	Organization LL facilitator
1	1	Identification and monitoring of emerging risks	WFSR	UNEW
2	3	Holistic risk assessment and acceptance	INRAE	UNEW
3	6	Novel digital infrastructure for food safety	AGROKNOW	EUFIC

2.1.2 Role LL manager and facilitator

For each LL, a LL manager and LL facilitator have been appointed. The responsibilities are defined as follows:

- LL manager: responsible for the coordination of LL activities and stakeholders. The LL manager is responsible for putting together the LL team and stakeholder group, following outlines provided by the HOLiFOOD Guidelines (D4.1) and for running the workshops etc. More specifically, the LL manager will organize the workshops, materials, rooms etc.; will record the workshops and LL activities; will analyse results; and will provide information for dissemination of results (WP7) while fostering the networking among the participants.
- LL facilitator: responsible for facilitating the discussions and knowledge exchange within the LL. A LL facilitator will coach the working group, lead workshops and surveys, communicate the rules/guidelines, foster the co-creation atmosphere, facilitate group dynamics and steer discussions, and will help to shape the outputs of the LL.

In order to structure the Living Lab activities, each of the three managers, starting from the definition and criteria of the Living Labs, structured a specific methodology that would best suit the specific objectives set in the exploration workshop. For LL1 and 3 it was an interactive workshop approach, while for LL2 it was a Delphi survey. LL managers and facilitators of the three LL were instructed how to conduct their activities by WP4, based on the guidelines as described in Deliverable 4.1.

2.1.3 Focus of the LLs Implementation

The overall aim of the LL is to *co-create tailor-made action plans addressing the stakeholder needs* as related to the LL topic. Each LL goes through the following three phases of Exploration, Experimentation and Evaluation.

1. Round 1 (M12): Exploration focuses on priority setting of each Lab as basis for the action plan. [This can be equated to an inductive research phase in a classic scientific research methodology]
2. Round 2 (M24): Experimentation, to Discuss and verify the action plan, and to monitor mid-term. [This can be equated to hypothesis setting and deductive phases in a classic scientific research methodology]
3. Round 3 (M36): Experimentation, idem [Iteration, and indeed this may have both inductive and deductive elements, suggesting an abductive method.]
4. Round 4 (M48): Evaluation, to discuss and evaluate the output of the LL process and provide recommendations for further exploitation. [This can be equated to the synthesis and conclusion phase in a classic scientific research methodology]

The first phase of each LL focuses on “Priority setting of each LL as a basis for the setup of the action plan”. Specifically, for each LL the Exploration phase concerned:

1. **LL1:** identification of needs of stakeholders as related to ERI models, what are their needs, how to address these, problems encountered.
2. **LL2:** identification of stakeholder's expectations in term of holistic risk assessment dimensions, preferential methods of risk aggregation, formats of holistic assessment outputs.
3. **LL3:** identification of technical requirements of stakeholders related to the ERI infrastructures, such as in terms of data, models and computation etc.

2.2 Methodology and implementation of Living Labs

2.2.1 Methodology of LLs

Starting from EnoLL's proposed definition of Living Lab highlighted in section 2.2 of this document, a specific methodological approach was tailor-made for the three HOLIFOOD LLs.

LL1 and LL3 were structured co-creation activities carried out within a workshop. The workshop format fostered a collaborative and participatory environment in which stakeholders could easily work together in an interactive way, and creatively contribute to the discussion about the topics explored. This approach aligned with WP1 and 6 objectives, ensuring a productive and inclusive exchange of ideas that were able to feed WP1 on the needs for ERI models and WP6 on the needs related to the technical user requirements.

LL2 used a well-established systematic user co-creation approach, the Delphi Survey. Through this approach, WP3/LL2 covered three main topics:

1. The specific scope of each case-study and associated mitigation strategies
2. The prioritization of risk and benefits by stakeholders
3. The formats of the holistic assessment outputs.

All materials required to implement the co-creation approach in LL2 were prepared by UNEW with inputs from INRAE, DTU, UVMB and WU (D3.1).

Various Delphi techniques can be used for both quantitative and qualitative data collection and identification of agreement and disagreements in relation to specific issues. They are appropriate techniques for collecting, aggregating and analysing the informed judgements of a group or panel of experts or other groups where information about experts is required on previously identified issues.

The Delphi method was considered the best approach to reach the LL2 objectives because it allows to collect and catalyse group judgments while avoiding the negative effects related to interpersonal biases, strong personalities, defensive attitudes and unproductive disagreements. Indeed, this method employs an iterative process of summarising, averaging, and recycling panel members' views to encourage convergence on a consensus view.

Throughout the process, in the light of the general opinions expressed by the panel, each expert is given the opportunity to revise earlier answers and change his or her opinion without the risk of embarrassment. The risk of feeling too exposed is also avoided thanks to another characteristic of the Delphi approach, which is the anonymity.

For all these reasons, using this approach for LL2 was considered the best option to collect the information needed to feed data to other WP3 tasks and obtain the expected results. This is also confirmed by the literature, as Delphi has repeatedly been used to investigate factors influencing decision-making on a specific issue, topic or strategy area in mobility policy¹. It has also been used in food safety policy specifically².

¹ D. M. Z. Islam et al., 2006; D. M. Z. D. M. Z. Islam & Zunder, 2014; Kembro et al., 2017; von der Gracht, 2012.

² Kendall et al., 2018; Wentholt et al., 2010.

2.2.2 Implementation of LLs

Below the implementation of each of the three LL is outlined.

- a. LL1: Setting up of a workshop featuring presentation about four main issues: A workshop was held at the Synergy Days held the 5th October 2023 in Greece. Topics discussed included: Capabilities of emerging risk prediction tools; Priority hazards and factors to be screened for; Requirements for a successful prediction model; Source data to be used as inputs for a prediction tool.
- b. LL2: Phase 1 (Survey): Inductive research using Delphi method as both scoping and data gathering exercise, necessary to feed data to other WP3 tasks and postulate theories. After developing the survey, it was launched in Qualtrics in June 2023, with a deadline for the first round at end August. Almost 100% of the stakeholders responded. The analyses of the first-round results was done during Sept/Oct 2023, with preliminary findings fed to other WP3 tasks. Further Delphi rounds (1-2) will continue as the work proceeds to move through further inductive and deductive phases.
- c. LL3: A workshop was held at the Synergy Days held the 5th October 2023 in Greece, back-to-back with the workshop for LL1. The workshop featured presentations on the use of Artificial Intelligence in the food industry from both academic and tech-company perspectives, followed by an open discussion on the necessary technical requirements and the challenges organizations are encountering.

2.3 Stakeholders involved in exploration phase Living Labs

Each LL was composed of at least 15 stakeholders, recruited by LL managers, with support of the LL facilitators, following the HOLIFOOD Guidelines (D4.1). The LL stakeholder group was as much as possible balanced in representing actors operating in the food safety risk sector, e.g. research, laboratories, food safety services, consumers, industry and farmers associations, and communicators. Gender balance was taken into account.

2.3.1 Stakeholder list exploration phase LL1

Data on the countries of provenance and stakeholder category were gathered from participants through a poll on the Woo Clap smartphone app. Participants' answers were anonymous: this was consistent with the Chatham House Rules under which the workshop was operated. The participants were informed of these rules at the start of the poll and were asked to consent to these rules in the first question.

These are the results concerning the participants' nationality (numbers in brackets):

1. Greece (9)
2. Serbia (3)
3. Spain (2)
4. Netherlands (2)

5. Austria (1)
6. France (1)
7. South Africa (1)

The following list includes the participants' field of operation (numbers in brackets):

1. Food safety (4)
2. AI for food safety (2)
3. Agri-food (2)
4. Agri-tech (2)
5. Communication(s) (2)
6. Food traceability (1)
7. Food technology transfer / safety culture / history (1)
8. Food industry R&D (1)
9. Business consulting (1)
10. Academic research (1)
11. Government (1)

2.3.2 Stakeholder list exploration phase LL2

The stakeholder group of LL2 was made up of 90% academics or full-time researchers, and 10% from food safety authorities or agencies; see Table 2. All these stakeholders were sent the Delphi survey.

Table 2: Stakeholders list for LL2

Organization name	Category	Men/Women
DTU	Academics / Food safety agencies	M
DTU	Academics / Food safety agencies	F
DTU	Academics / Food safety agencies	F
DTU	Academics / Food safety agencies	F
INRAE	Academics	M
INRAE	Academics	F
INRAE	Academics	M
INRAE	Academics	F
UNIVIE	Academics	F
UNIVIE	Academics	F
UVMB	Academics / Food safety agencies	M
UVMB	Academics / Food safety agencies	F
UVMB	Academics / Food safety agencies	F
UVMB	Academics / Food safety agencies	F

WU	Academics	M
WU	Academics	F
WU	Academics	F
UNEW	Academics	M
UNEW	Academics	M
UNEW	Academics	F
Dialogik	Not-for-profit research institute	M
BfR Bund	Regulatory scientific organization	F

Nationally the panel was split evenly between Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom. In terms of experience the panel had a good range: 42% of respondents had 1 to 10 years of experience, about 42% had 11-20 years of experience and around 16% had 21 years or more.

It is important to note that due to the anonymity of the Delphi approach, it is not possible to confirm the makeup of the panel in the same way of LL1 and LL3; nevertheless, this anonymity is viewed as having yielded more objective insights: respondents were in fact unaffected by peer pressure and charisma/age/gender characteristics of others, as it happens in open workshops and forums.

Figure 1 and 2 present the demographic of the survey participants. They include the type of organization, the country in which they work and the gender of participants.

Figure 1: Organisation type and Country of work for panel

Q4 - How many years of experience do you have in your role?

Q5 - How do you describe yourself?

Figure 2: Years of experience and gender identity of the panel

After the Delphi Survey, an online workshop to discuss results was organized on 28 February 2024. Participants to this workshop included 16 external people and 6 internal members of the consortium.

2.3.3 Stakeholder list exploration phase LL3

Through the Wooclap smartphone app, the 33 workshop participants of the LL3 workshop entered answers to poll questions, including questions about their country of origin (Figure 3) and field of work (Figure 4). No attribution was made in the answers in the Wooclap to the individual participants, consistent with the Chatham House Rules under which the workshop was operated.

Figure 3: Poll outcome on participant's origin

Various countries were represented (numbers of participants in brackets):

- Greece (6)
- Serbia (1)
- Poland (3)

- Mexico (1)
- Netherlands (3)
- Spain (1)
- United Kingdom (1)
- France (1)
- South Africa (1)
- Germany (1)
- Romania (1)
- Ireland (1)

Several sectors were represented in the LL3 stakeholder group, amongst others 8 stakeholders from the Food safety, two from Agrifood innovation sector, two from the Data analysis and data science sectors; and two from the Dissemination sector.

Figure 4 Poll outcome on field work origin of participants

Several external experts have been involved in the LL3 workshop directly by AGROKNOW, supported by APRE, as shown in Table 3.

Table 3: List of external experts from AGROKNOW

Organization name	Category	Social category	Men/ Women	Country
Technical University of Cartagena/Spain	Academics	Professor	M	SP
Technical University of Cartagena/Spain	Academics	Researcher	M	SP
Mega Yeeros	Poultry Industry	Research & Development Specialist	F	GR

Mega Yeeros	Poultry Industry	Quality Assurance Director	F	GR
INRAE	Research	Researcher	F	FR
Agritrack	Tech company/research	AI engineer	M	GR
Lamia Stevia	Industry and Farmers	Agronomist	M	GR
Intrasoft	Tech company	AI engineer	M	GR
Effost	Food safety agency	Project & Communications Manager	F	NL
Effost	Food safety agency	Managing director	M	NL
Biocos/ Watson	Research	Researcher	F	GR
Wikifarmer	Industry and Farmers	Agronomist, Plant Science	F	GR
Wikifarmer	Industry and Farmers	Agronomist, Plant Science	F	GR
Agricultural University of Athens	Research	Agronomist	F	GR

The consistent number of participants coming from Greece is justified by the fact that the Synergy days were held in Thessaloniki (Greece), hence it was easier for Greek stakeholders to participate in presence to the event. This, however, did not influence the Living Labs in any way for the heterogeneity of the expertise that the stakeholders brought to the workshop tables.

2.4 Process of the LLs

The following sections present the process of the Exploration activity of each LL, with one section per LL, including the workshop held at the Synergy days of LL1 and LL3, and the Delphi survey held in the course of LL2. Annex 1 presents the announcement of the two workshops at the Synergy days. At the Synergy days, an information booth on the HOLiFOOD project was organized as well, as shown in Figure 5 below.

Figure 5: Project booth staffed by HOLiFOOD partners during the Synergy Days

2.5 Process LL1

Welcome and introduction

As shown in Figure 6 below, WP1 leader Wenjuan Mu (WFSR) provided the background of the HOLiFOOD project and introduced the concept of a holistic approach for building a food safety emerging risk identification system, with an emphasis on the importance of combining knowledge from different fields in food and agriculture and data science knowledge when constructing such a system.

00:15 Ice breaker questions in Wooclap

Workshop participants were asked to access the Wooclap website on their smartphones to answer poll questions. The Wooclap poll was operated by Naomi Dam and colleagues from WUR. The first questions (#1-#3) were of a general nature, asking about participants' provenance and field of work. Questions and results were also displayed on the main screen, with moderation by Tom H. Zunder from UNEW (Figure 7).

00:20 Questions about emerging risk identification systems

The following questions (#4-#17) concerned the use of AI for the development and usage of predictive tools for emerging food safety risks, such as the use of AI, the kinds of hazards to be scrutinized, data sources, etc. Results were shown as bar diagrams or word clouds, depending on the type of question.

00:50 Summary, conclusion, and discussion

The workshop moderator wrapped up the polls, summarized the main observations and conclusions, allowing participants to raise comments and questions to animate the discussion.

Figure 6: Welcome and introduction to the workshop by W. Mu

Figure 7: Moderation of the workshop by T. H. Zunder

2.6 Process LL2

Within LL2, input was collected from expert by using a traditional Delphi consisting of the following steps:

1. **Scoping:** this step implies asking experts and stakeholders to scope baselines, metrics, factors and other elements that they view as important in the estimation of food risk in general, and more specifically in the HOLiFOOD supply chains of Legumes, Maize and Chicken. This step was carried out through anonymous online surveys.

2. **Exploring Consensus.** In this step, the information collected in the first step through the Delphi method was elaborated in order to understand the views of experts in terms of consensus and dissent about food risks, regulations and policies.
3. **Workshop.** A workshop was run to validate, expand, nuance and critique the outputs from anonymous survey work. The virtual workshop was organized on February 28, 2024 to receive feedback on the structure of the survey and on the relevance of the interim results collected through the survey.

2.7 Process LL3

Welcome and introduction

Presentation by Maria Scherbov (EUFIC), providing info for the purpose of the workshop.

Ice breaker questions in Wooclap

Workshop participants were asked to access the Wooclap website on their smartphones for answering poll questions. The poll was operated by Naomi Dam and her colleagues from WUR. The first questions were of a general nature, asking about participants' provenance and field of work. Questions and results were also displayed on the main screen, with moderation by Maria Scherbov (EUFFIC).

Questions about novel digital infrastructure for food safety in Wooclap

A series of follow-up questions were posed.

Summary, conclusion, and discussion

The moderator wrapped up the poll results and summarized the main observations and conclusions, allowing participants also to raise any comments or questions they'd like to share with other participants and the hosts.

3 Results

3.1 Results Living Lab 1

The LL1 stakeholder group of the workshop was composed as: approximately a ~50/50 division of users and developers of tools amongst the audience (+- 20 people).

The poll and discussion outcomes were the result of participants views, their experiences, and recommendations regarding the technical features of emerging risk prediction tools, providing project partners with a view on users' and developers' needs and preferences.

This LL allowed to establish connections with experts and representatives of parallel projects.

The visibility of the project was enhanced through the distribution of promotional materials (brochures, merchandise) at the project booth and several relevant contacts were collected.

The experts' views/recommendations on the following aspects were retrieved. Results are summarized in the Figures:

- Capabilities of emerging risk prediction tools (Figure 8)
- Priority hazards and factors to be screened for (Figure 9)
- Requirements for a successful prediction model (Figure 10)
- Source data to be used as inputs for a prediction tool (Figure 11)

Figure 8: Poll outcome: capabilities of emerging risk prediction tools

The answers given by participants in the poll and the active discussion that took place afterwards, which extended over the expected time, confirmed the stakeholders' interest for the topic and the high level of engagement created. A positive surprise was the participants' interest in the field of AI for food safety.

Workshop results will serve as a basis for further development of AI tools within HOLIFOOD WP1.

3.2 Results Living Lab 2

The first phase of the Delphi survey can be described as a productive session, in which at times the collective anonymous opinions of the peers were unexpected. The participants observed that the results prompted them to reassess the priorities and decisions they had planned for their work. It was acknowledged that this added value, but also that researchers were experts and whilst this Delphi process may inform their research planning, in the end they should adopt approaches that are defensible, practical and in line with contractual obligations.

The workshop conducted on 28 February 2024 was necessary to receive feedback on the structure of the survey and on the relevance of the interim results collected. In the survey's questions, a high degree of consensus with regard to emerging risks, their identification and the metrics used to monitor them was seen; For all questions with statements that did not reach consensus, they should be repeated as before as is the case with classic Delphi methodology.

The survey also showed evidence of the need to move towards sustainable, healthy and inclusive food systems. By doing this, co-benefits can be delivered also for climate mitigation and adaptation, environmental sustainability, and circularity, sustainable healthy nutrition, safe food consumption, food poverty reduction, the inclusion of marginalised people, the empowerment of communities, and flourishing businesses.

Specific results and insights of the survey results are detailed fully in D3.1.

3.3 Results Living Lab 3

Three main questions were asked to stakeholders to get feedback. Answers to these questions are summarized in the figures below:

- a. Which opportunities may arise in the organization represented regarding possible applications of AI technologies (Figure 12)
- b. What are the technical requirements for implementing AI in the organizations (Figure 13)
- c. What are the challenges you are facing within the implementation of AI (Figure 14)

In general, the main outcomes of the stakeholder discussion highlighted different aspects:

- Stakeholders showed trust in AI and underlined that understanding AI nowadays is imperative
- Importance of input factors for predictive microbiological models
- A comprehensive approach to food safety assessment is needed
- Relevance of precision sensors and accurate estimations
- Leveraging data to enhance model outcomes is essential

The visibility of the project and the networking possibility were enhanced through the distribution of promotional materials (brochures, merchandise) thanks to the targeted project boot.

Figure 12: Wooclap activity's result for the question "What opportunities do you think AI tools present to your organization for food safety?"

Figure 13: Wooclap activity's result for the question "What are the specific technical requirements your organization needs to implement AI?"

Figure 14: Wooclap activity's result for the question "What challenges are you currently facing in implementing AI in your organization?"

The LL3 workshop yielded significant insights into key aspects of food safety, emphasizing the need for trust and understanding of AI and the importance of leveraging data to enhance model outcomes. These insights will guide us in the forthcoming workshop, where we will delve deeper into these issues, preparing relevant questions for our next phase of Living Labs.

3.4 Participants' feedback and additional inputs for implementation

3.4.1 Reflections on LL1 and LL3

At the end of the activities, surveys were submitted to the LL1 and LL3 workshop participants asking them to evaluate LLs 1 and 3 carried out on site and to specify what works well and what does not to find possible implementation points for future LLs.

The overall rate of appreciation was very positive (highest level) for both LLs.

Some of the strengths of the activities were the moderation, which was rated as engaging by the participants and kept the audience's attention high throughout the session. Furthermore, through the workshop and the information marketplace (project stand by the HOLiFOOD partners), contacts were established that can be used for follow-up surveys, interviews and other events.

The activities (workshops, stands, pitch talks, prize competitions) helped to increase the visibility of the HOLiFOOD project among colleagues involved in agricultural data research.

Finally, collaboration with the Stellar's sister project on the identification of emerging risks in the production environment and food supply chain helped to reach a wider audience (two consecutive workshops on the same morning; the workshop reported here was the

second). This point was particularly effective as both projects hosted consecutive workshops on the same morning, and the workshop reported here was the second.

The workshop facilitated valuable networking opportunities, creating connections that could be exploited for future surveys, interviews and events. The various activities, including workshops, project stands, pitch talks and prize competitions, significantly increased the visibility of the HOLIFOOD project (and Stellar) within the agricultural data research community.

At the same time, the activities and the final discussions were crucial and will serve as starting point to implement the next LLs. In this regard, something that did not work well was that no personal data of the participants in the room were collected (only voluntarily, according to Chatham House rules): instead, personal data would be necessary to engage interested stakeholders in future events and keep them updated on the project developments.

From a technical point of view it can be mentioned that the Wooclap app for the surveys did not give the expected results, as it had to be restarted several times during the activities before working correctly. Alternative applications will be considered for the future.

Another negative aspect was the noise pollution from neighbouring rooms that was impossible to avoid due to the contiguity of the available spaces.

Finally, the competition factor of parallel workshops was a disadvantage in terms of time, space and materials to be used, but was successfully overcome.

3.4.2 Reflections on LL2

Concerning LL2, different strengths and possible weaknesses emerged. Specifically, what particularly worked were the following points:

- The anonymity of polls allowed free contribution, permitting dissent
- Asynchronous online involvement avoided unsustainable travel
- Asynchronous online involvement increased participation and allowed for catching up and filling gaps.

On the other hand, some weaknesses concerned the fact that Delphi surveys may tend to confirm the status quo (LL2).

Furthermore, the anonymity of the surveys allows free input, and this might lead to outlandish dissent. Nevertheless, this aspect was not found in this specific phase of the Delphi survey.

Finally, using an English language survey can be a barrier for non-native speakers to argue and justify their answers.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

The feedback obtained during the LL1 workshop greatly aided in gauging the needs and preferences of prospective end users and tool developers. Notably, the audience contained a balanced mix of participants from both these target groups and their answers and discussion points were indicative of their knowledgeability in the field. Participants views, experiences, and recommendations regarding the technical features of emerging risk prediction tools, provided project partners with a view on users' and developers' needs and preferences. Information and data collected will be crucial to steer the development of ERI tools within WP1 and will serve as basis for the next phase of LLs.

Round 1 of the LL2 Delphi survey showed a high degree of consensus with regard to identification of and metrics used to monitor emerging risks.

Together with Tasks 3.2 and 3.3, the first phase of LL2 work contributed to reinforcing the capacity and expertise for risk assessment activities including holistic risk assessment (risks in combination with benefits) and improving the support for food systems regulatory science (integrated risk-benefit assessment, cost-benefit assessment) through robust holistic risk assessment. The results collected through anonymous and asynchronous involvement will be used by WP3 team to inform the work in WP3.4 and WP 5.2.2.

The outcomes and discussions of LL3 workshop emphasized the significance of establishing trust in artificial intelligence, underscoring the importance of transparency and reliability in AI applications. The workshop promoted a comprehensive approach to food safety, acknowledging the need to consider multiple dimensions and stakeholders: the need for data accuracy and relevance in enhancing food safety assessments was underlined; the incorporation of precision sensors for accurate estimations emerged as a promising avenue for future advancements; the importance of leveraging data to enhance model outcomes was emphasized, highlighting the potential for data-driven improvements. Lastly, the imperative of understanding AI was reiterated, as knowledge and awareness are essential for responsible implementation. These outcomes will serve as the foundation for the next round of LL3.

5 Set up and planning next steps Living Labs

5.1 Next steps LL1

To plan the next LL1 activities, WP1 and WP4 teams will conduct an internal evaluation of the first workshop. Furthermore, an in-depth survey will be held in parallel, as part of LL1, possibly complemented with expert interviews.

5.2 Next steps LL2

Further rounds of Delphi surveys will continue as the work proceeds to move through further inductive and deductive phases. The analysis will complete by end June 2024, results will be analysed by the end of August 2024, and findings will already inform WP3.4 and WP5.2.2.

5.3 Next steps LL3

To plan the next LLs phase AGROKNOW will develop a set of questions derived from the outcomes from the first exploration phase workshop, after an internal evaluation of the first LL made by WP6 and WP4 teams.

AGROKNOW also plans to participate again in the Synergy Days event, which presents an excellent opportunity to engage with and gather insights from experts in the field.

6 Annex 1. Announcement of LL1 and LL3 workshop

Living Lab #1	“Emerging food safety risks”
Workshop #	1
Date	4-5 October 2023
Location	Thessaloniki, Greece (part of the Synergy Days 2023)
Lab Manager(s)	Gijs Kleter
Lab Facilitator(s)	Tom Zunder (lead facilitator), with help of Naomi Dam, Wenjuan Mu, Leonieke van den Bulk, Maria-Eleni Dimitrakopoulou, Maria Scherbov

Living Lab #3	“Novel Digital Infrastructure for Food Safety”
Workshop #	1
Date	5 October 2023
Location	Thessaloniki, Greece (part of the Synergy Days 2023)
Lab Manager(s)	Maria-Eleni Dimitrakopoulou
Lab Facilitator(s)	Maria Scherbov (lead facilitator), with help of Manos Karvounis, Gijs Kleter, Tom Zunder , Naomi Dam, Wenjuan Mu, Leonieke van der Bulk

7 Annex 2. Preview of LL2 Delphi Round 1 Survey

- I consent, begin the study
- I do not consent, I do not wish to participate

In what sort of organisation do you work?

- Policy maker
- Academic/research organization
- Food industry (Food Manufacturer, Food ingredient supplier, Toll packer, etc)
- Food regulatory agency
- Food safety authority/agency
- Multinational/global organization
- Non-government organization (NGO)
- Other, enter free text below

In which country do you work?

How many years of experience do you have in your role?

How do you describe yourself?

- Male
- Female
- Non-binary / third gender
- Prefer to self-describe
- Prefer not to say

Please indicate the degree to which you consider to be a priority for risk evaluation in Europe, each of the following emerging risks, including those to human health and the environment. (Swipe left and right between risks and select one statement from the vertical stack.)

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Nutrition (e.g., reduced micronutrients, protein density)	<input type="radio"/>				
Invasive fungi species	<input type="radio"/>				
Invasive plant species	<input type="radio"/>				
Invasive animal species (including, insects)	<input type="radio"/>				
Mycotoxins	<input type="radio"/>				
Radioactive contamination	<input type="radio"/>				
Chemical contamination of foods	<input type="radio"/>				
Plant diseases (e.g., viral diseases)	<input type="radio"/>				
Food Authenticity	<input type="radio"/>				
Animal diseases	<input type="radio"/>				
Microbiological contamination of foods	<input type="radio"/>				
Zoonotic diseases	<input type="radio"/>				
Anti-microbial resistance	<input type="radio"/>				
Veterinary drugs residues	<input type="radio"/>				
Other hazards/risk (please state)	<input type="radio"/>				
<input type="text"/>					

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Other hazards/risk (please state) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>				

Please indicate the importance of the following drivers of emerging food risks in Europe? (Swipe left and right between risks and select one statement from the vertical stack.)

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Response to and mitigation of climate change	<input type="radio"/>				
Resource scarcity and use efficiency	<input type="radio"/>				
Food system shock	<input type="radio"/>				
Policy changes (e.g. the EU Green Deal, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Demographic changes (e.g., population growth, population ageing, migration)	<input type="radio"/>				
Changes in consumer demand	<input type="radio"/>				
Labelling of food (e.g., expiration, allergens, etc.)	<input type="radio"/>				
Changes in logistical movement and transport of food and agricultural products	<input type="radio"/>				
Economic driving forces (e.g., globalisation of the food web, increased food prices)	<input type="radio"/>				
Increased intensification of food production	<input type="radio"/>				
Technological driving forces (eg., new technologies such as Gene editing, Nanotechnology in packaging, meat substitutes)	<input type="radio"/>				
Geopolitical driving forces (e.g., war)	<input type="radio"/>				
Changes in globalisation (e.g., deglobalisation)	<input type="radio"/>				
Societal values (e.g., animal welfare , fair trade, environmental protection)	<input type="radio"/>				
Malevolent activities (e.g. fraud, introduction of counterfeit products, food bioterrorism, etc)	<input type="radio"/>				
Increased complexity and size of the supply chain	<input type="radio"/>				
Food risk representation in the media/ social media (e.g. increasing or decreasing societal concern about specific food risks).	<input type="radio"/>				
Water security (e.g. drought, pollution, flooding).	<input type="radio"/>				
Soil health abuses/negligence (e.g eutrophication events)	<input type="radio"/>				
Political will (e.g. not allocating resources or policy agendas to food safety issues)	<input type="radio"/>				
Other drivers (please specify) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>				
Other drivers (please specify) <input type="text"/>	<input type="radio"/>				

Please indicate the extent to which you think that each of the drivers is an important influence on **INCREASING** the incidence of emerging food risks. (Swipe left and right between drivers and select one, many or no risks from the vertical stack.)

	Microbiological contamination of foods	Chemical contamination of foods
Response to and mitigation of climate change,	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Resource scarcity and use efficiency	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Food system shock	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>